

THE PHENOMENON OF ABDULATIF MIRZA: AS SCIENTIST AND POET

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Annotation. In this article, Abdulatif Mirza's scientific and creative activities, personal participation in cultural life are studied and analyzed based on historical sources. Some comments were made about Abdulatif Mirza's participation in literary processes.

Key words and phrases: Abdulatif Mirza, cultural life, literature, art, observatory, astronomy, patronage, poetry, scientific meeting.

I. INTRODUCTION. Abdulatif Mirza was a political person who was energetic and determined by nature and could fight for his goals. He was distinguished by his sharp decisions and actions.

II. LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. W. Barthold, D. M. Dunlop, E. Brown, J. Aubin, B. Gray, T. W. Lentz, K. M. Maitra, Ismail Aka, M. Carey, M. Subtelnu, F. Richard et al. This issue is partially addressed in the works of researchers and scientific research [1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10]. In particular, Eduard Braun gave a high assessment of his activities in the cultural sphere and noted that he was a patron of science and the founder of a book-writing school. The works of historians such as Nizamiddin Shami, Sharafuddin Ali Yazdi, Muiniddin Natanzi, Hafizi Abru, Fasikh Khavafi, Abdurazzaq Samarkandi, Davlatshah Samarkandi, Mirkhand, Khondamir were used in the study of the selected issue [11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18, 19]. A number of important historical information related to the researched issue is reflected in the cited sources.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. Davlatshah Samarkandi, referring to the personality of the prince, mentioned that he was brought up in the palace of Shahrukh Mirza from a young age, and that his grandfather treated him better than other grandsons [152]. The author noted that his position in the palace was higher than other princes. In our view, Abdulatif Mirza was seen as one of the heirs to the throne. T. Fayziev says that the prince also participated in reception ceremonies of foreign ambassadors and gives a number of interesting information about him. Of course, the personality of Abdulatif Mirza was greatly influenced by Gavharshadbegim. In 1441, his relationship with prince Gavharshadbegim deteriorated and he went to Samarkand to Mirza Ulugbek [324]. The cooling of relations between them can be attributed to two factors. The first was the support of Alouddavla Mirza, the eldest among the princes, by Gavharshod Begim, while the second was in his jizzak. However, in 1442, Gavharshadbeg came to Samarkand and took the prince with him to Herat.

Alisher Navoi describes Abdulatif Mirza in his work "Majolisun-nafais" as follows: "...a commercial customer and a meticulous and generous person. I had other strange vices than mine, and you need to be modest. Otar killed the sage and king's father for the advice of the

world. Every mirror, the kingdom was loyal to Shiruyaga. But his taste was reciting and he recited poetry well" [4]. At the same time, a masnavi written by him is also cited:

Бар дилу жон сад бало аз як назар овард чашм,
Чун бигуям шукри ин, ё раб, набирад дард чашм.

Davlatshah Samarkandi wrote about the prince in "Tazkirat ush-shuaro" "...He won the heart by showing honor to his father in his miserable head. But the devil again led him astray and made him want to kill his father," he writes [151]. Abdulatif Mirza was ambitious and difficult, but also talented and educated. It is stated in the sources that he patronized the development of science like Mirzo Ulug'bek, and liked to debate with scientists and poets. He was engaged in history, catastrophe, poetry. Even though the prince acquired worldly knowledge, he strictly followed religious laws and showed respect to religious leaders and dervishes [325].

T. Fayziev talks about his grandson Sharafuddin Ali Yazdi, who rebelled against Shahrukh Mirza in 1446, who served in the court of Sultan Mohammad Mirza, who was imprisoned among the rebels and was rescued by the prince. After that, Abdulatif Mirza sent the historian to Herat. Abdulatif Mirza was one of the gifted princes, who was stubborn and ambitious, but who appreciated people of science and liked to talk with scientists and poets. He was engaged in history, poetry, science of catastrophes. Fakhri Hiravi describes Abdulatif Mirza as "wise, dense and knowledgeable, pleasant".

In 1446, Shahrukh Mirza suppressed the rebellion of Sultan Muhammad and punished those around him. Among them was Ali Yazdeen, whom Abu Latif Mirza rescued and sent to Herat with the exiles. Like his father, he studied astronomy in depth and was able to make an astrological chart. He must also have observed the celestial bodies. According to Hasankhoja Nisari, Mirzo Ulughbek's great-grandson, son of Kochkinchikhan, Abdulatif Khan, was also well versed in the science of catastrophes and gathered scientists who were engaged in the science of astronomy in his court. We believe that the study of astronomy and the observation of celestial bodies continued gradually among the representatives of the dynasty.

IV. CONCLUSION. It should be said that it is important to study Abdulatif Mirza's participation in political processes, his activities in the field of science and culture. Abdulatif Mirza is like other princes.

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